

Complex Compounds of Substituted Thioureas. Part III. Copper Derivatives of Mono- and Di-*N*-acetylthioureas

S. N. Bauerjee and A. C. Sukthankar

Several complex compounds of mono- and di-*N*-acetylthioureas with different copper salts have been prepared under varying experimental conditions and their properties studied. The problem of constitution of these complexes has been reviewed and criticised.

Siddhanta and Banerjee¹ have mentioned that a large number of solid copper thiourea and copper-substituted thiourea compounds exist in literature, where copper ion shows a diversity in the co-ordination number and in some cases, fractional molecules of thiourea per metal ion are present. These have been grouped in *nine* different classes¹.

Morgan and Burstall² have suggested that thiocarbamide due to presence of three co-ordinating ligands, viz., two amino radicals and a thiocarbonyl group, exerts a dual character and leads not only to mononuclear cuprous salt but also to more complex polynuclear derivatives, in which amino groups of thiocarbamide probably serve as bridging units. Though both N and S are present in the molecule, yet co-ordination through S atom functioning as donor has been suggested in these cases by Haworth and Mann³, Prasad and Srivastava⁴, and Sahasrabuddhey and Krall⁵. Recent infrared studies, however, infer that there can be two types of co-ordination, one through the sulphur as in the thiourea complexes of Pt (II), Pd (II), and Zn (II) and the other, *probably* through the nitrogen as exemplified by Cu (I), Pt (II), and Pd (II) in the methylthiourea complexes⁶. Yaffe and Voigt⁷, on the contrary, from spectrophotometric study of some ruthenium—thiourea systems have postulated a four-membered chelate ring structure for these complexes. This structure, however, is not expected to be sufficiently stable due to steric reasons and seems to be quite improbable. Siddhanta and Banerjee⁸ have considered the bridging property of thiourea molecule through the linkage of the S-atom in it to two metal atoms by two co-ordinate bonds, viz.,

where sulphur attains tetra-avalency. The gradual decomposition of the compounds formed between concentrated Fehling solution and certain thioureas to insoluble copper

1. *This Journal*, 1961, **38**, 747.
2. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 143.
3. *Ibid.*, 1943, 661.
4. *This Journal*, 1958, **35**, 793.
5. *Ibid.*, 1942, **19**, 25; 1944, **21**, 83.
6. Yamaguchi *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **80**, 527; 1959, **81**, 3824.
7. *Ibid.*, 1952, **74**, 2503.
8. *This Journal*, 1961, **38**, 765.

sulphide as also their decomposition at about 100° (or with alkali solution, *vide* Experimental) to black copper sulphide, which has been observed by Dehn⁹, further supports the formation of S → M bonds in these complexes. It may also be remarked that smaller electron density on N in "amino group" than on S in "thiocarbonyl group" as well as greater ionisation potential of N (14.5 e.v.) over S (10.36 e.v.) will account for the lesser co-ordinating power of the former. Moreover, co-ordination through N will also be hindered by the steric effect of the substituents in the amino group of the ligand. Thus formation of thiourea bridge

as suggested by Siddhanta and Banerjee¹⁰ is justified and hence thiourea co-ordinates through the sulphur rather than through the nitrogen, thus occupying only one co-ordination position.

As an extension of the previous work¹⁰, a study has been made in the present investigation on the formation of solid complexes between mono- and di-*N*-acetylthioureas and different copper salts with a view to ascertaining stability and nature of the solid complexes formed under varying conditions of temperature, pH, dielectric constant of the medium, and varying number of substituents in the ligand since these are of interest in studying the co-ordinating tendencies of various substituted thiourea ligands¹⁰.

The only compounds reported¹ between copper and mono-*N*-acetylthiourea (AcTh) are: Cu₂SO₄.4AcTh, 4CuCl.7AcTh, 2CuCl.3AcTh, CuOH.AcTh.0.5 H₂O. In the present work nine new solid compounds have been presented: CuOH.2AcTh, CuOH.3AcTh, CuOH.4AcTh, CuCl.2AcTh, CuCl.2.5AcTh, CuCl.3AcTh, CuCH₃COO.AcTh, CuCH₃-COO.2AcTh, CuCH₃COO.3AcTh besides Cu₂SO₄.4AcTh reported earlier¹. With di-*N*-acetylthiourea (AcThAc), however, all attempts to prepare more than two stable compounds, CuCl. 2AcThAc and CuCH₃COO. 4AcThAc, have failed presumably due to easy hydrolytic susceptibility of this thiourea derivative. The combining power of the mono-*N*-acetyl ligand to copper (I) is probably affected, besides other factors, by the chemical nature of the anions, sulphate, acetate, hydroxide and halide, and this is evident from different types of copper (I)-*N*-acetylthiourea complexes reported in this paper.

EXPERIMENTAL

N-Acetylthiourea was prepared by the method of Neucki¹¹, m.p. 165. (Found: N, 23.52. Calc. for CH₃CONHCSNH₂: N, 23.73%). It is soluble in water and highly soluble in ethanol, acetone, and ether. The compound is quite stable.

9. *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, **62**, 3189.

10. Lane *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1959, **81**, 3569; Walter *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1956, **78**, 5560.

11. *Ber.*, 1873, **6**, 599.

Di-*N*-acetylthiourea was prepared by a known method¹², m.p. 153°. (Found: N, 17.43. Calc. for $C_5H_8O_2N_2S$: N, 17.5%). The compound is sparingly soluble in cold water, but rapidly hydrolyses when heated in aqueous solution. It is quite stable.

Copper Derivatives of N-Acetylthiourea

Bis-(*N*-acetylthiourea)-*copper Hydroxide*.—A faintly ammoniacal solution (25 ml) of copper sulphate (3 g.) was added slowly with stirring to an aqueous solution (200 ml) of *N*-acetylthiourea (2 g.), when the solution turned green and an olive-green precipitate was formed. The compound was filtered after keeping for 20 mins. It was then washed with water and finally with ethanol, dried, and analysed. [Found: Cu, 20.25, 20.12; N, 17.55, 17.76; S, 20.30, 20.15. $CuOH.2(CH_3CONHCSNH_2)$ requires Cu, 20.08; N, 17.69; S, 20.21%].

The compound changes from olive-green to brown on drying. The compound is stable towards cold HCl (dil.), but hot dilute solution of HCl or NaOH decomposes it. It is insoluble in water, ethanol, or chloroform but sparingly soluble in acetone.

Tris-(*N*-acetylthiourea)-*copper Hydroxide*.—An aqueous solution (20 ml) of copper sulphate (2 g.) was made slightly alkaline with a dilute ammonia solution. This was then added slowly at room temperature to an aqueous solution (400 ml) of *N*-acetylthiourea (3.5 g.), when an olive-green precipitate was formed. The mixture after keeping for half an hour was filtered, washed with water, then with ethanol, dried in air, and analysed. [Found: Cu, 14.59, 14.65; N, 19.40, 19.31; S, 22.13, 22.17. $CuOH.3(CH_3CONHCSNH_2)$ requires Cu, 14.63; N, 19.33; S, 22.09%].

The same compound was formed in a faintly ammoniacal medium at ice temperature (45 mins.) using aqueous solutions of *N*-acetylthiourea (250 ml, 2 g.) and of copper sulphate (20 ml, 1.5 g.). (Found: Cu, 14.54, 14.70; N, 19.21, 19.40; S, 21.92, 22.16%).

The compound is olive-green in colour but changes to brown on progressive drying. It does not react with cold dilute HCl, but hot acid decomposes it. With dilute NaOH solution it turns black. It is insoluble in water, ethanol, acetone, or chloroform.

Tetrakis-(*N*-acetylthiourea)-*copper Hydroxide*.—To *N*-acetylthiourea (3.5 g.), dissolved in 95% ethanolic solution (300 ml) at 0°, was added slowly with stirring an ice-cold, slightly alkaline solution (25 ml) of copper sulphate (1 g.), when a green precipitate turning to chocolate was formed. The mixture was kept at 0° for about 30 mins., filtered, washed with ice-cold water and then with ethanol, dried in air, and analysed. [Found: Cu, 11.30, 11.41; N, 20.09, 20.18; S, 23.26, 23.02. $CuOH.4(CH_3CONHCSNH_2)$ requires Cu, 11.50; N, 20.27; S, 23.16%].

The compound is stable and melts at 175°. It does not react with cold dilute HCl, but hot acid decomposes it to a black residue. It is also decomposed slowly by cold dilute NaOH but rapidly with a hot solution to a black residue. The substance is insoluble in water, ethanol, and chloroform but slightly soluble in acetone.

Bis-(N-acetylthiourea)-copper Chloride.—An ice-cold aqueous solution of cupric chloride (3 g.) was added slowly with stirring to an ice-cold aqueous solution of *N*-acetylthiourea (6 g.), when a pale yellow flocculent precipitate was formed. The mixture was kept at ice temperature for about 30 mins., filtered, washed successively with cold water and ethanol, dried in vacuum, and analysed. [Found: Cu, 19.01, 19.04; N, 16.65, 16.70; Cl, 10.62, 10.56; S, 19.20, 19.22. $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2(\text{CH}_3\text{CONHCNSNH}_2)$ requires Cu, 18.98; N, 16.72; Cl, 10.59; S, 19.11%]. The same compound was prepared in an identical condition at room temperature. (Found: Cu, 18.96, 19.00; N, 16.66, 16.69; Cl, 10.57, 10.61; S, 19.16, 19.18%).

The compound is stable and melts at 186°. It does not react with cold dilute HCl. With NaOH solution it is decomposed and turns black. The substance is insoluble in water, ethanol, acetone, or chloroform.

Pentakis-(N-acetylthiourea)-di-copper Chloride.—An aqueous solution of cupric chloride (50 ml, 7 g.) was added slowly with stirring to an aqueous solution of *N*-acetylthiourea (100 ml, 2 g.), when a pale yellow precipitate was formed. It was filtered after 20 mins., washed successively with water and ethanol, and analysed when dry. [Found: Cu, 15.96, 16.09; N, 17.50, 17.67; Cl, 9.02, 8.97; S, 20.16, 20.39. $2 \text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 5(\text{CH}_3\text{CONHCNSNH}_2)$ requires Cu, 16.14; N, 17.76; Cl, 9.00; S, 20.31%].

The compound is very stable; m.p. 230° (decomp.). It does not react with cold dilute HCl, but hot acid dissolves it, which on cooling gives a white flocculent precipitate. With NaOH solution it turns black. It is insoluble in water, ethanol, acetone, or chloroform.

Tris-(N-acetylthiourea)-copper Chloride.—An aqueous solution of cupric chloride (25 ml, 1.5 g.) was added slowly to that of *N*-acetylthiourea (400 ml, 7 g.) at room temperature, when a voluminous yellow precipitate was formed. On keeping the mixture for about $\frac{1}{2}$ hour, it was filtered, washed successively with water and ethanol, dried in air, and analysed. [Found: Cu, 13.92, 13.84; N, 18.30, 18.60; Cl, 7.69, 7.70; S, 21.02, 20.95. $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 3(\text{CH}_3\text{CONHCNSNH}_2)$ requires Cu, 14.04; N, 18.54; Cl, 7.77; S, 21.19%]. The same compound was formed between solutions of cupric chloride (25 ml, 1 g.) and *N*-acetylthiourea (150 ml, 5 g.) at the boiling temperature (5 mins.). (Found: Cu, 13.94, 13.99; N, 18.40, 18.51; Cl, 7.73, 7.69; S, 21.12, 20.98%).

The compound is very stable; m.p. 240° (decomp.). It resembles the previous compound in properties.

Tetrakis-(N-acetylthiourea)-di-copper (I) Sulphate.—To an aqueous solution (300 ml) of *N*-acetylthiourea (4.5 g.), made faintly alkaline with ammonia, was added slowly with stirring an aqueous solution (50 ml) of copper sulphate (2 g.), when a yellowish red precipitate was formed. The mixture was kept for about 15 mins. at room temperature, filtered, washed successively with water and ethanol, dried in air, and analysed. [Found: Cu, 18.40, 18.45; N, 16.20, 16.25; S, 23.12, 23.07; $\text{Cu}_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 4(\text{CH}_3\text{CONHCNSNH}_2)$ requires Cu, 18.29; N, 16.11; S, 23.01%]. The same compound was, however, prepared by Siddhanta and Banerjee¹ at ice-temperature in a moderately strong ammoniacal medium using a different molecular ratio and it was found by the authors that it showed a very low paramagnetic susceptibility value ($\mu_B \approx 0.33 \text{ B.M.}$) which confirms the formula represented above. The compound melts at 190°.

Mono-(N-acetylthiourea)-copper Acetate.—An aqueous solution (150 ml) of cupric acetate (8 g.) was added slowly with stirring to an ethanolic solution (200 ml, 50%) of *N*-acetylthiourea (4 g.), when a greyish black compound was formed and the solution turned deep blue. The mixture was kept for about an hour with occasional stirring. It was then filtered, washed successively with water and ethanol, dried in vacuum, and analysed. [Found: Cu, 26.29, 26.51; N, 12.02, 12.25; S, 13.04, 13.21. $\text{CH}_3\text{COOCu} \cdot \text{CH}_3\text{CONHCSNH}_2$, requires Cu, 26.42; N, 12.19; S, 13.29%].

The compound is stable and melts with decomposition at 170°. It does not react with cold dilute HCl, but hot acid dissolves it, which on cooling gives a white flocculent precipitate. It is decomposed by dilute NaOH, especially when warmed, with the formation of a black residue. The compound is insoluble in water, ethanol, or chloroform but slightly soluble in acetone.

Bis-(N-acetylthiourea)-copper Acetate.—To *N*-acetylthiourea (4.5 g.), dissolved in water (300 ml), was added slowly with stirring an aqueous solution (100 ml) of cupric acetate (3 g.). The solution changed from yellowish green to deep blue in colour and a greyish white compound was formed. The mixture was kept for about $\frac{1}{2}$ hr., filtered, washed with water and acetone, dried in air, and analysed. [Found: Cu, 17.58, 17.80; N, 15.55, 15.43; S, 17.70, 17.92. $\text{CH}_3\text{COOCu} \cdot 2(\text{CH}_3\text{CONHCSNH}_2)$, requires Cu, 17.73; N, 15.62; S, 17.84%]. The substance resembles the previous compound in properties and melts at 190°.

Tris-(N-acetylthiourea)-copper Acetate.—An ice-cold aqueous solution of cupric acetate (1 g.) was added slowly to an ethanolic (30%, 300 ml) solution of *N*-acetylthiourea (7 g.) at the same temperature, when the solution changed from white to pale green and finally a pale yellow compound was precipitated. The mixture was kept in ice for $\frac{1}{2}$ hr., filtered, washed successively with ice-cold water and ethanol, dried in air, and analysed. [Found: Cu, 13.06, 13.25; N, 17.54, 17.70; S, 19.97, 20.08. $\text{CH}_3\text{COOCu} \cdot 3(\text{CH}_3\text{CONHCSNH}_2)$, requires Cu, 13.35; N, 17.63; S, 20.15%].

The substance resembles mono-(*N*-acetylthiourea)-copper acetate in all properties except that it is insoluble in acetone; m.p. 160°.

Copper Derivatives of Di-N-acetylthiourea

Bis-(Di-N-acetylthiourea)-copper Chloride.—A solution of cupric chloride (2 g.) in anhydrous acetone (100 ml) was added slowly with stirring to a solution (100 ml) of di-*N*-acetylthiourea (5 g.) in the same medium at about 0°, when a deep red solution was formed. The colour gradually changed to orange and finally an orange-yellow compound was precipitated. The mixture was kept for about 15 mins. with occasional stirring, filtered, washed with ice-cold acetone, dried in air, and analysed. [Found: Cu, 15.05, 15.30; N, 13.15, 13.27; Cl, 8.59, 8.61; S, 15.07, 15.21. $\text{CuCl} \cdot 2(\text{CH}_3\text{CONHCSNHCOCH}_3)$, requires Cu, 15.17; N, 13.37; Cl, 8.46; S, 15.28%].

The compound does not react with cold dilute HCl, but dissolves in hot acid. It is decomposed by dilute alkali, especially when warmed, forming a black residue and the solution turns bluish green. The compound is sparingly soluble in water, ethanol, acetone, or chloroform and melts at 175°.

Tetrakis-(di-N-acetylthiourea)-copper Acetate.—A 50% acetone solution (100 ml) of cupric acetate (2.5 g.) was added slowly with stirring to an acetone (50 ml) solution of di-N-acetylthiourea (3 g.) at room temperature, when the solution changed from yellow to deep red in colour and a yellowish orange precipitate was formed. After 30 mins. the solution was filtered and the precipitate was thoroughly washed with acetone. It was dried in air and analysed. [Found: Cu, 8.31, 8.30; N, 14.75, 14.81; S, 16.82, 16.69. $\text{CH}_3\text{COOCu}\cdot 4(\text{CH}_3\text{CONHCSNHCOCH}_3)$ requires Cu, 8.34; N, 14.69; S, 16.78%].

The compound is insoluble in water, ethanol, acetone, or chloroform and resembles the previous compound in other properties. It does not react with cold dilute HCl, but hot dilute acid or alkali solution decomposes it.

The authors wish to express with appreciation their indebtedness to Prof. S. K. Siddhanta, Section of Geochemistry, for suggesting the problem. They also wish to acknowledge with appreciation the interest shown by Prof. G. M. Nabar, Director, Department of Chemical Technology, University of Bombay, and by Prof. S. K. Bhattacharyya, Head of the Department of Applied Chemistry, Indian Institute of Technology, Kharagpur, in the investigations reported here.

DEPARTMENT OF APPLIED CHEMISTRY,
INDIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY,
KHARAGPUR
AND
INORGANIC CHEMISTRY LABORATORY,
DEPARTMENT OF CHEMICAL TECHNOLOGY,
UNIVERSITY OF BOMBAY, BOMBAY-19.

Received November 23, 1961